

Tool Artifact for “Generalized Program Sketching by Abstract Interpretation and Logical Abduction”

Aleksandar S. Dimovski¹

Mother Teresa University, st. Mirche Acev nr. 4, 1000 Skopje, North Macedonia

Abstract. In this work, we describe the installation, usage, and evaluation results of the tool, denoted **GenSketching**, introduced by the paper “Generalized Program Sketching by Abstract Interpretation and Logical Abduction”. We provide step-by-step instructions on how to download, run, and compare the tool’s outputs to outputs described in the paper. The tool is a research prototype program sketcher for resolving numerical program sketches in C using abstract interpretation and logical abduction. It uses a combination of forward and backward numerical analyses based on abstract interpretation to generate constraints that are solved by using the logical abduction technique.

1 Introduction

This work summarises the evaluation results reported by the paper “Generalized Program Sketching by Abstract Interpretation and Logical Abduction”. We compare three tools:

- **GenSketching** that uses a combination of forward and backward numerical analyses based on the Polyhedra domain from the APRON library [7], while the abduction and SMT queries are solved by the EXPLAIN [2] and the MISTRAL [3] tools.
- The **Sketch** version 1.7.6 [9,8] that uses SAT-based inductive synthesis.
- The **FAMILYSKETCHER** [6] that uses lifted (family-based) static analysis by abstract interpretation based on the Polyhedra domain.

2 Downloading

The URL of the tool artifact is available from
The files inside this folder are:

- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/8165119>.
- Google Drive: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1PV_OZFFvvhkiLTlojPe8sQy9UIfM9iEp?usp=sharing.

Once you download all files, use 7-Zip to restore VM image “Ubuntu18.ova”. The virtual machine containing the tool installed and ready to use is “user”: aleks, “password”: aleks.

3 Experimental Results

* For step-by-step execution of all test cases of the tools follow:
ExperimentalResults.txt

3.1 GenSketching

* Enter the folder that contains the tool
cd gen_sketcher

* Recompile the tool by using the following two commands (see also “Compiling GenSketching” subsection from “HowToInstall.txt”):

```
eval $(opam config env)
ocamlbuild ml_float.o Main.native -use-ocamlfind -use-menhir
-pkgs 'bddapron,apron,gmp,oUnit,zarith' -I utils -I banal -I domains -I frontend
-I main -libs boxMPQ,octD,polkaMPQ,str,zarith,bddapron -lflags banal/ml_float.o
```

To run GenSketching on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

Note that after commands in square brackets we write:

- the total times in seconds on our machine to complete the given synthesis task, and
- the time taken to solve the given abduction queries by calling EXPLAIN.

```
$ ./Main.native -domain polyhedra bench/intro.c
result: [0.0022 sec] [0.0011]
$ ./Main.native -domain polyhedra bench/abs.c
result: [0.0021 sec] [0.0013]
$ ./Main.native -domain polyhedra bench/while.c
result: [0.0055 sec] [0.0013]
$ ./Main.native -domain polyhedra bench/max.c
result: [0.0042 sec] [0.0011]
$ ./Main.native -domain polyhedra bench/max2.c
result: [0.0040 sec] [0.0015]
$ ./Main.native -domain polyhedra bench/cond.c
result: [0.0019 sec] [0.0011]
$ ./Main.native -domain polyhedra bench/mine.c
result [0.0757 sec] [0.0012]
$ ./Main.native -domain polyhedra bench/mine2.c
result [0.0059 sec] [0.0013]
```

3.2 FamilySketcher

* Enter the folder that contains the tool
cd ..

cd family_sketcher

* Recompile the tool by using the following two commands (see also “Compiling FamilySketcher” subsection from “HowToInstall.txt”):

```
eval $(opam config env)
ocamlbuild Main.native -use-ocamlfind -use-menhir -pkgs 'apron,gmp,oUnit,zarith'
-I utils -I domains -I frontend -I main -libs boxMPQ,octD,polkaMPQ,str,zarith
To run FAMILYSKETCHER on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we
write the following commands.
```

Note that after commands in square brackets we write: the total times in seconds on our machine to complete the given synthesis task. For each benchmark, we perform two analyses: one for 5-bit sizes of holes, and one for 10-bit sizes of holes.

```
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/intro.c
result: [0.0013 sec] 5-bit version
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/intro-10.c
result: [0.0016 sec] 10-bit version
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/abs.c
result: [0.0020 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/abs-10.c
result: [0.0021 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/while.c
result: [0.0047 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/while-10.c
result: [0.0053 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/max.c
result: [0.0025 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/max-10.c
result: [0.0026 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/max2.c
result: [0.0022 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/max2-10.c
result: [0.0033 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/cond.c
result: [0.0021 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/cond-10.c
result: [0.0023 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/mine.c
result [0.0035 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/mine-10.c
result [0.0042 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/mine2.c
result [0.0024 sec]
$ ./Main.native -tree -domain polyhedra bench/mine2-10.c
result [0.0031 sec]
```

3.3 Sketch

```
* Enter the folder that contains the tool
cd ..
```

```
cd sketch-1.7.6
cd sketch-frontend
```

To run Sketch on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands. Note that after commands in square brackets we write the reported times in seconds on our machine. For each benchmark, we perform two analyses: one for 5-bit sizes of holes, and one for 10-bit sizes of holes.

```
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/intro.sk
result: [0.208]
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 10 --bnd-inbits 10 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/intro.sk
result: [0.239]

$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/abs.sk
result: [0.204]
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 10 --bnd-inbits 10 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/abs.sk
result: [0.236]

$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/while.sk
result: [FAILS] with 8 unrollments of the loop
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 10 bench/while.sk
result: [0.213] with 8 unrollments of the loop
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 10 --bnd-inbits 10 --bnd-unroll-amnt 10 bench/while.sk
result: [0.224]

$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/max.sk
result: [0.229]
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 10 --bnd-inbits 10 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/max.sk
result: [24.25]

$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/max2.sk
result: [0.227]
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 10 --bnd-inbits 10 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/max2.sk
result: [31.88]

$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/cond.sk
result: [1.216]
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 10 --bnd-inbits 10 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/cond.sk
result: [2.362]

$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/mine.sk
result: [0.236]
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 10 --bnd-inbits 10 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/mine.sk
result: [1.221]

$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 5 --bnd-inbits 5 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/mine2.sk
result: [0.215]
$ ./sketch --bnd-cbits 10 --bnd-inbits 10 --bnd-unroll-amnt 8 bench/mine2.sk
result: [1.217]
```

Table 1. Performance results of `GenSketching` vs. `Sketch` vs. `FAMILYSKETCHER`. All times in sec. `GenSketching` and `FAMILYSKETCHER` use Polyhedra domain. All times in sec. All experiments are executed on a 64-bit 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1165G7 CPU@2.80GHz, VM LUbuntu 18.04 with 8 GB memory. All times are reported as average over five independent executions. For `Sketch` and `FAMILYSKETCHER`, we report results for 5-bit and 10-bit sizes of domains of holes.

Bench.	GenSketching		Sketch		FAMILYSKETCHER	
	TIME	ABDTIME	5-bits	10-bits	5-bits	10-bits
<code>intro.c</code>	0.0022	0.0011	0.208	0.239	0.0013	0.0016
<code>abs.c</code>	0.0021	0.0013	0.204	0.236	0.0020	0.0021
<code>while.c</code>	0.0055	0.0013	0.213	0.224	0.0047	0.0053
<code>max.c</code>	0.0042	0.0011	0.229	24.25	0.0025	0.0026
<code>max2.c</code>	0.0040	0.0015	0.227	31.88	0.0022	0.0033
<code>cond</code>	0.0019	0.0011	1.216	2.362	0.0021	0.0023
<code>mine.c</code>	0.0757	0.0012	0.236	1.221	0.0035	0.0042
<code>mine2.c</code>	0.0059	0.0013	0.215	1.217	0.0024	0.0031

4 Extensibility

The tool is written in OCAML and consists of around 7K LOC. Currently, it provides only a limited support for arrays, pointers, `struct` and `union` types. The abstract operations and transfer functions of the numerical abstract domains (e.g. Polyhedra [1]) are provided by the APRON library [7], while the abduction and SMT queries are solved by the EXPLAIN [2] and the MISTRAL [3] tools. The tool is built on top of the `Function` [10] for proving program termination and the DSPLNUM²ANALYZER [5] for analyzing `#if`-enriched C programs with numerical features.

In the folder “frontend”, the lexer and parser are implemented. In the folder “main”, the files “Main.ml” and “SingleAnalysisIterator” describe the main program from which the tool performs analysis of the given sketch and the implementation of the forward and backward analyses. The tool can be easily extended and new options can be added.

References

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